

Synthesis, spectroscopic, electrochemical and anti-HIV studies of some mononuclear and dinuclear Fe^{III} complexes of 3-hydroxy-4'-benzyloxy flavone containing oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur donors as co-ligands

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Complex of Fe^{III} with 3-hydroxy-4'-benzyloxy-flavone (LH) (1) was allowed to react with DMSO (2), 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (MBZH) (3), sodiumdithiocarbamate (NaDTC) (4) and pentane-2,4-dione (acacH) (5) respectively. Resulting complexes were characterized by IR, UV/Vis, ESR, Mössbauer spectral techniques, elemental analysis, FAB mass data and magnetic moments. Electrochemical behaviour of free ligand (LH) as well as anti-HIV activities of the complexes have also been studied.

Flavones are known for a variety of medicinal applications¹⁻³. Although most of the flavones are natural products, yet synthetic flavones have also been found as antimicrobial agents against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis* together with antifungal activities⁴ against *C. albicans*, *T. mentagrophytes* and tumours⁵. Beside their biological applications, flavones, especially 3-hydroxy flavones possess bidentate chelating sites which have been exploited for the formation of metal complexes especially of Cu, Zn and Pt⁶⁻⁸ and antimutagenic properties of quercetin complexes with platinum metals have also been reported⁹. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new complexes of hydroxy flavone with Fe^{III} ion in continuation of our earlier studies on ruthenium complexes¹⁰ and keeping in view that Fe^{III} is a congener of Ru^{III} ion. Additionally, it has also been reported¹¹ that several donors used as co-ligands affected the properties of the metal complexes directly or indirectly therefore co-ligands bearing N,N, N,S, O,O, O,S donors sets have also been incorporated in the complexes of Fe^{III} with flavone.

Results and discussion

Compositions of the complexes assigned on the basis of their elemental analysis and FAB-mass data are shown in Table 1. Representative FAB mass pattern of complexes 3 and 4 are shown in Fig. 1. Complexes were found to be soluble in DMF and DMSO. Molar conduc-

tances of the complexes recorded in DMF (10⁻³ M), showed their non-electrolytic nature in solution.

IR spectral peak observed at 1242 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of free flavone (LH) assigned as δ_{OH} vibration¹² disappeared in the spectra of the complexes (1-5) indicating that deprotonated OH group of the flavone coordinated with the metal ions. Additionally, $\nu_{C=O}$ of LH observed at 1640 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1604-1602 cm⁻¹ together with ν_{C-O-C} skeletal vibration of LH observed at 1280 cm⁻¹ which also shifted to 1255 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes supporting coordination of $>C=O$ group with the Fe^{III} ion. Since no peak due to DMSO appeared in the spectrum of the complex 2 so its coordination with the metal ion has been discarded. In the spectrum of 3, peak due to ν_{SH} did not appear, as observed in the spectrum of free MBZH and 2573 cm⁻¹ which indicated that probably deprotonated SH group coordinated with the metal ion. However, $\nu_{C=N}$ vibration¹³ observed at 1512 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of free MBZH shifted to 1493 indicating that $\nu_{C=N}$ group had coordinated with the metal ion. The characteristic peak of free dithiocarbamate observed at 1064 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{C=S}$ shifted to 1016 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the complex 4 supporting bidentate coordination¹⁴ of dithiocarbamate with the metal ion. Presence of coordinated 2,4-pentanedione in the spectrum of 5 is assigned by the observation of a peak at 1580 cm⁻¹ due to ($\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=O}$) vibrations¹⁵. Additionally, its spectrum of the complex 1 also showed a peak at 951 cm⁻¹

Table 1. Physical properties and FAB mass data of the Fe^{III} complexes

Complexes	FAB-mass data Found (Calcd.)	Yield % colour	Calcd. (Found)					
			C	H	N	Cl	S	Fe
[Fe(L) ₂ (Cl)(H ₂ O)], 1	797 (792)	60 Black	66.24 (66.79)	3.76 (4.16)	-	4.45 (4.27)	-	7.35 (7.40)
[Fe(L) ₃], 2	1088 (1088)	40 Brown	72.79 (72.84)	4.13 (4.70)	-	-	-	5.14 (5.24)
[Fe ₂ (L) ₂ (MBZ) ₂ (μ-OH) ₂], 3	1132 (1132)	35 Brown	61.48 (61.88)	3.71 (3.93)	2.47 (2.41)	-	5.67 (6.56)	9.80 (10.25)
[Fe ₂ (L) ₂ (DTC) ₂ (μ-OH) ₂], 4	1132 (1132)	35 Brown	46.64 (46.82)	4.50 (4.12)	2.47 (2.60)	-	11.30 (12.29)	9.89 (10.29)
[Fe ₂ (L) ₂ (acac) ₂ (μ-OH) ₂], 5	1036 (1036)	30 Brown	62.54 (62.84)	4.60 (4.56)	-	-	-	10.81 (11.80)

Fig. 1. FAB mass spectra of complexes : (a) [Fe₂(L)₂(MBZ)₂(μ-OH)₂]; **3** and (b) [Fe₂(L)₂(DTC)₂(μ-OH)₂]; **4**.

due to coordinated water¹⁶ whereas the peak observed at 900 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes **3**, **4** and **5** were assigned as ν_{Fe-OH-Fe}^{17,18}. Due to poor resolution of the spectra in the lower region, ν_{M-O}, ν_{M-N}, ν_{M-S} vibrations could not be distinguished from free ligand vibrations observed in the same regions.

UV/Vis spectral data observed in DMF (10⁻⁵ M) in the region 200–800 nm are shown in Table 2. In general, four transitions are observed in the region 260–272, 328–368, 416–432 and 480–484 nm and these multiplet transitions could be assigned as intraligand and L → M charge transfer transitions. Multiple transitions observed in the spectra of the complexes may arise due to their highly asymmetrical nature though the spectral features were found very similar to those reported for high spin Fe^{III} octahedral complexes¹⁹. Broad peak observed at 370–375 nm has been identified in some μ-hydroxo complexes²⁰.

Magnetic moment data calculated for the complexes at room temperature (RT) are shown in Table 3 and the values are found in the range reported²¹ for high spin Fe^{III} complexes. However, the curve obtained by plot-

Table 2. Electronic absorption spectral data of ligand and its Fe^{III} complexes

Compds. ^a	λ _{max} , (nm), (ε _{max} × 10 ⁻³)							
LH	228 (45);	248 (43);	312 (34);	348 (58)				
1	260 (12)sh;	312 (12);	336 (14);	352 (15);	368 (14);	416 (12);	482 (3)vw	
2	252 (6) sh;	312 (12);	330 (14);	411 (10);	487 (12);	592sh(9)		
3	272 (13)sh;	308 (9);	332 (10);	348 (10);	416 (5);	484 (1)vw		
4	270 (18)sh;	312 (9)vw;	332 (7)vw;	352 (7)vw;	428 (4)w;	484 (2)vw		
5	276 (15)sh;	308 (12)vw;	332 (10);	352 (9);	368 (8);	432 (8);	463 (1)sh;	506sh(3)

^aComplex details are listed in Table 1.

sh = shoulder, vw = very weak.

Table 3. ESR spectral parameter and μ_{eff} of the Fe^{III} complexes

Complexes ^a	g-Values		Solution LNT	Magnetic moment; μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 296 K
	Solid state			
	RT	LNT		
1	-	$g_x = 5.30$ $g_y = 3.39$ $g_z = 2.12$	$g_{\parallel} = 6.40$ $g_{\perp} = 4.45$	6.6
2	-	-	$g_x = 4.19$ $g_y = 2.94$ $g_z = 1.92$	5.9
3	$g_x = 11.05$ $g_y = 5.82$ $g_z = 3.86$	-	$g_x = 4.94$ $g_y = 2.35$ $g_z = 1.95$	4.3
4	$g_{\parallel} = 6.86$ $g_{\perp} = 4.03$	-	$g_x = 4.64$ $g_y = 3.12$ $g_z = 2.04$	5.6
5	-	-	$g_x = 9.88$ $g_y = 2.81$ $g_z = 1.92$	5.9

^aComplex details are listed in Table 1.

RT = Room temperature, LNT = Liquid nitrogen temperature.

ting magnetic moments vs temperature for the complex 3 at -25°C , -50°C , -100°C , $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$, $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$ and for 4 at which, -20°C , 23°C , 40°C , 50°C , 60°C temperatures are shown in the Figs. 2a and 2b respectively which indicated that in the complex 3, two Fe^{III} ions are coupled antiferromagnetically whereas in complex 4, nature of curve is similar to that reported for paramagnetic complexes²².

ESR spectrum of the complex 1 recorded in solid state at liquid N_2 temperature (LNT) showed anisotropic feature and g tensors were found as $g_x = 5.30$, $g_y = 3.39$ and $g_z = 2.12$. A representative ESR spectrum of the complex 3 in the solid state at room temperature (RT) is shown in Fig. 3. The feature of the spectrum is associated with high spin iron(III) ($S = 5/2$), species as reported earlier for other Fe^{III} complexes²³ and the corresponding g -values calculated for the complexes are shown in Table 3. The magnitude of g -values are contrary to that of typical d^5 (^6S) compound where g_{iso} lies at 2.0. This could be considered in terms of strong-field splittings as reported earlier by Griffiths²⁴. Signals giving g -values ≈ 4.0 may arise from parallel field transitions within both $\pm 5/2$ and $\pm 1/2$ Cramer's doublet and $\approx g = 6.0$ could be associated with parallel field transitions within $\pm 5/2$ doublets, whereas $g = 3.0$ may arise with perpendicular-field transition with $\pm 5/2$ and $\pm 1/2$ doublets but g -value observed at ≈ 9.0 could be considered in view of

Fig. 2. Variation of magnetic moments of the complexes w.r.t. temperature (K) : (a) $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{MBZ})_2(\mu\text{-OH})_2]$; 3 and (b) $[\text{Fe}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{DTC})(\mu\text{-OH})_2]$; 4.

Wickman's plot as reported earlier^{21,25}.

The Mössbauer spectra were recorded with a constant acceleration spectrometer (Austin, Science Associates). Data were stored in a 1024-channel Pulse-height analyzer (type 5200; Inotech Inc). The temperature was

Fig. 3. Solid state ESR spectrum of the complex $[Fe_2(L)_2(MBZ)_2(\mu-OH)_2]$; **3** at RT.

monitored with a calibrated copper-constantan thermocouple within a variable temperature cryostat (type ASAD-4V). A cobalt 57 source of 10 mci diffused into a palladium foil was used for the absorption measurement. All spectra were fitted by Lorentzian line shapes using a least squares fitting procedure at the computer, Kyushu University, Japan. The velocity scale was normalized with respect to the centre of the spectrum of metallic iron at 296 K. The quadrupole splittings of the low and high spin doublets in these fits were kept constant at 2.85 and 0.28 $mm\ s^{-1}$ respectively. Mössbauer spectra of the complexes showed very weak absorption even at 78 K which could be understood in terms of bonding of the flavone (LH) with the metal through oxygen donors as reported earlier for $Fe(acac)_3$ complex²⁶. A representative Mössbauer spectrum observed for the complex **3** is shown in Fig. 4 giving value of $\delta_{Fe} = 0.192\ mm\ s^{-1}$, $\Delta E_Q = 0$. The isomer shift lies in the range as reported for high spin Fe^{III} complex²⁷.

Fig. 4. Mössbauer spectrum of complex $[Fe_2(L)_2(MBZ)_2(\mu-OH)_2]$; **3**.

Thus, based on elemental analysis, FAB mass data and spectral properties, the proposed structures of the complexes are shown in Fig. 5a. Since single crystals of the complexes suitable for their X-ray crystallographic studies could not be grown, structures of the complexes **1**, **2** and **5** have been simulated on the basis of MM2 force fields and are shown in Fig. 5b.

L = Deprotonated 3-hydroxy-4'-benzyloxy flavone; **1**

L = Same as above; **2**

L = Same as above; L' = MBZ; **3**

L = Same as above; L' = DTC⁻; **4**

L = Same as above; L' = acac; **5**

Fig. 5a. Proposed structure of the complexes.

The electrochemical behaviour of free ligand (LH) and its Fe^{III} complexes were studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV) in DMF solution ($10^{-3}\ M$) using TBAP (0.1 M) as supporting electrolyte and Ag/Ag^+ as reference electrode and redox potential data of LH and their iron complexes are reported in Table 4 along with a representative cyclic voltammogram of the complex **1** as shown in Fig. 6. As shown in the Fig. 6(a) complex **1** showed one irreversible oxidation at +0.96 V along with two irreversible reductions at -0.57 and -1.15 volts. However, electrochemical behaviour of the free ligand (LH) was also observed to be similar except that oxidation potential of the

Fig. 5b. Simulated molecular structure of (a) complex 1, (b) complex 2 and (c) complex 5. For clarity all hydrogens and carbon atom labels have been omitted.

complexes was observed at lower potential, supporting the coordination of the ligand (LH) with the metal ion.

Anti-HIV activity :

From Table 5 it is evident that complex 4 showed 50% toxicity at 51.0 (IC₅₀) µg/ml whereas complex 2

Table 4. Electrochemical data of free ligand (LH) and Fe^{III} complexes*

Compd. ^a	Oxidation <i>E</i> _{ox} /V	Reduction <i>E</i> _{red} /V
LH	+1.16	-0.60, -0.20
1	+1.00	-1.05, -0.72
2	+0.72	-0.94, -0.53
3	+0.86	-0.86, -0.36
4	0.92	-0.88, -0.36
5	+1.10	-0.92, -0.44

^aComplex details are listed in Table 1.

*At scan rate 100 mV/s.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of the complexes [Fe₂(L)₂(Cl)(H₂O)]₁: (a) 0.0 – -1.50 V region, (b) 0.0 – +1.06 V.

showed EC₅₀ at 0.908 µg/ml, which also showed with therapeutic index as 58.6. Thus, it could be inferred from the data that incorporation of flavone brought highest activity by the substitution of chlorine and H₂O present in complex 1. Complex 3, containing benzimidazole as co-ligand, showed better activity, consistent with an earlier report²⁹. Furthermore, complex 2 showed higher

Table 5. Anti-HIV activity of Fe^{III} complexes

Complexes	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	EC ₅₀ (µg/ml)	Therapeutic index
1	65.600	No suppression	No suppression
2	53.200	0.908	58.600
3	73.400	No suppression	No suppression
4	51.000	No suppression	No suppression
5	66.600	No suppression	No suppression
AZT	500.000	0.020	24800

AZT = Azidothymidine, IC₅₀ = Inhibitory concentration for 50%, EC₅₀ = Effective concentration, No suppression = No viral replication.

therapeutic index as compared to earlier reported complexes from our own laboratory³⁰ and all complexes except 2 did not show suppression of viral replication as compared to AZT though their IC₅₀ values changed significantly with the variation of co-ligands. However, this surmise calls for deeper investigations.

Experimental

Solvents were distilled prior to their use. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone, 4'-benzyloxy-benzaldehyde, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole, sodiumdiethyldithiocarbamate and 2,4-pentanedione were purchased from Aldrich whereas FeCl₃.3H₂O and DMSO were purchased from Merck. Flavonol (LH) was prepared by reported procedure³¹ and commercial (Fluka) tetra-butylammonium bromide was converted into pure tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) using reported procedure³².

Synthesis of complexes :

Ethanol solution of FeCl₃.3H₂O (1 mmol, 0.26 g) was added to a solution of LH (1 mmol, 0.34 g) in 15 ml (EtOH : DMSO, 1 : 1 v/v) and then refluxed for 12 h. After the reduction of volume upto 5 ml, solid thus obtained was filtered, washed several times with EtOH followed by ether then dried *in vacuo* and characterized as 1. The dried complex 1 (0.5 mmol, 0.12 g) was allowed to react separately with DMSO (5 ml), 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (0.5 mmol, 0.07 g), sodium dithiocarbamate (0.5 mmol, 0.07 g) and 2,4-pentanedione (1.0 ml) respectively and corresponding solutions were then refluxed for 8 h which were precipitated by the addition of water and separated as 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively. Complexes were purified by column chromatography using neutral alumina as column support and CH₃CN, aqueous KNO₃-water (7 : 1 : 0.5 v/v) as eluents³³. Eluates thus obtained were concentrated and residues were then dissolved in acetone and reprecipitated by water. Corresponding crys-

talline solids obtained by filtration were washed successively with H₂O, EtOH and Et₂O and then dried *in vacuo*.

Physical measurements were made as described earlier¹¹.

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References

1. T. Akama, H. Ishida, Y. Shida, U. Kimura, K. Gomi, H. Saito, E. Fuse, S. Kobayashi, N. Yoda and M. Kasai, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1997, **40**, 1894.
2. M. E. Zwaagstra, H. Timmerman, A. C. Van de Stolpe, F. J. J. de Kanter, M. Tamura, Y. Wada and M. Q. Zhang, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1998, **41**, 1428.
3. C. Gnerre, U. Thull, P. Gaillard, P. A. Carrupt, B. Testa, E. Fernandes, F. Silva, M. Pinto, M. M. M. Pinto, J. L. Wolfender, K. Hostettmann and G. Cruciani, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **84**, 552.
4. C. Y. Ragasa, Z. Pendon, V. Sangalang and J. A. Rideout, *Philipp. J. Sci.*, 1999, **128**, 347.
5. T. Akama, K. Ueno, H. Saito and M. Kasai, *Synthesis*, 1997, 1446.
6. J. Stawinska and M. Cieslak-Golonka, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 153.
7. G. Speier, V. Fülöp and L. Parkanyl, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 512.
8. E. Balogh-Hergovich, G. Speier and G. Argay, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 551.
9. B. S. Crombie, C. Smith, C. Z. Varnavas and T. W. Wallace, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2001, 206.
10. L. Mishra and A. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1288.
11. L. Mishra and A. K. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1826.
12. R. M. Silverstein, G. C. Bassler and T. C. Morrill, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley Pub., 1991, p. 25.
13. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley Pub., 1978, p. 339.
14. F. Bonati and R. Ugo, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, **10**, 257.
15. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley Pub., 1978, p. 251.
16. M. Abd El-Moaleb, Ramadan, M. Ibrahim, El-Mehasseb

- and R. M. Issa, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 529.
17. L. Mishra, M. K. Said and N. K. Jha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 917.
 18. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley Pub., 1978, p. 230.
 19. L. Duellund, R. Hazell, C. J. Mckenzie, L. P. Nielsen and H. Toftlund, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 152.
 20. D. M. Kurtz, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 585.
 21. G. R. Hall and D. N. Hendrickson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 607.
 22. H. A. Goodwin, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **18**, 293.
 23. D. H. Jo, Y. M. Chiou and L. Oue, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 3181.
 24. B. A. Goodman and J. B. Raynor in "Advances in Inorganic Chemistry and Radiochemistry", eds. H. J. Emeleus and A. G. Sharpe, Academic Press, 1970, **13**, 276.
 25. R. D. Bereman, M. L. Good, B. J. Kalbacher and J. Buttone, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 618.
 26. A. R. Champion, R. W. Vaughen and H. G. Drickamer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, **47**, 2583 and references therein.
 27. H. Oshio, K. Toriumi, Y. Maeda and Y. Takashima, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, **30**, 4252.
 28. U. Burkert and N. L. Allinger, "Molecular Mechanics", ACS, Washington DC, 1982.
 29. M. K. Said, L. Mishra, A. Richharia and R. S. Dubey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 2148 and references therein.
 30. L. Mishra, A. K. Yadav, R. S. Phadke, C. S. Choi and K. Araki, *Metal Based Drug*, 2001, **8**, 65.
 31. N. De. Meyer, A. Haemer, L. Mishra, H. K. Pandey, L. A. C. Pieters, D. A. Vanden Berghe and A. J. Vlietinc, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1991, **34**, 736.
 32. D. T. Sawyer, A. Sobkowiak and J. L. Robert (Jr.), "Electrochemistry for Chemist", Wiley, New York, 1995.
 33. E. C. Constable and A. M. W. C. Thompson, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1995, 1615.